

FACTORS AFFECTING ONLINE PURCHASE INTENTION AMONG UNDERGRADUATES IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

At present, the number of devices connected to the Internet is rapidly increasing, and their apps make it easy to access Internet services. The availability of Internet services has led to increased competitiveness in online shopping. Without any geographic and temporal restrictions, customers get the convenience of online shopping. However, they can't feel, touch or taste the physical product when they purchase it (Dharmesti et al., 2019).

Many previous studies have examined the factors affecting online purchase intention. It has been found that relative advantage, perceived website image, trust and perceived website reputation affect consumers' online shopping intention (Akrosh & Al-Debei, 2015). A research conducted in China revealed that Chinese consumers' age, income, education and marital status and perceived usefulness are significant factors influencing online shopping intention (Gong et al., 2013). Another study found that perceived internet confidence and search intention for information via the online store are important factors in consumers' online purchase intention (Hahn & Kim, 2009). Past literature reveals that even though there are previous research examining customers' purchase intention, those findings are not consistent. For example, Rahayu et al. (2018) and Khan & Rizvi (2011) found that there was a positive significant relationship between perceived risk and online purchase intention. Aref and Okasha (2020) found that there was a significant negative relationship between perceived risk and online purchase intention (Aref & Okasha, 2020). Gong et al. (2013) found that there was a non-significant relationship between perceived risk and online

purchase intention. Regarding other variables such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, trust etc., similarly mixed findings are visible. Thus, there is an apparent conflict of findings in previous research.

The technology acceptance model (TAM) has been used by many previous researchers in examining online purchase intention. However, such research is limited in the Sri Lankan context. Further, in general, there is a dearth of research examining the factors influencing online purchase intention using the TAM model with extended constructs.

Previous literature also indicates that very few studies examine young adults' online purchase intention. Young adults are considered as people who are in their twenties and thirties (Pelz, n.d.). Therefore, this study aims to investigate factors affecting online purchase intention among undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

The conceptual framework (see Figure 1) was developed for this study based on previous literature examined. The conceptual framework was primarily dependent on the TAM. Based on previous literature, the conventional TAM was extended by adding perceived usefulness and ease of use into the conceptual framework.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

This research followed a quantitative approach, and a cross-sectional survey was used to collect primary data from the desired sample. The sample included undergraduates from the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. The unit of analysis was undergraduates.

The target population of this research is students of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. There are 12650 undergraduates currently enrolled in six faculties in the university.

The convenient sampling method was selected for this study. Structural equation modelling was used as the Data analysis method of this study. The minimum sample size for the study was calculated as 161 (Soper, 2021).

The study used a questionnaire survey methodology, and the questionnaire items were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5). Smart PLS 3 was used for structural equation modelling.

Results and Discussion

Below table illustrates the summary of hypothesis testing.

Table 1: Summary of hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Path coefficient	P Values	Results on Hypotheses	Consistent/Inconsistent with previous literature
H1- There is a Positive effect of Perceived usefulness on Attitude towards internet use	0.439	0.000	Supported	Consistent with previous literature (Islam, et al., 2011; Zarrad & Debabi, 2012)

H2- There is a positive effect of Perceived ease of use on Attitude towards internet use	0.222	0.018	Supported	Consistent with previous literature (Islam, et al., 2011; Zarrad & Debabi, 2012; Zuelseptia, et al., 2018)
H3- There is a positive effect of Attitude towards internet use on online purchase intention.	0.428	0.000	Supported	Consistent with previous literature (Dharmesti, et al., 2019)
H4- There is a Negative effect of Perceived Risk on online purchase intention	0.057	0.254	Not supported	Inconsistent with previous literature (Aref & Okasha, 2020) (Rahayu, et al., 2018)
H5- There is a Positive effect of Trust on online purchase intention	0.419	0.000	Supported	Consistent with previous literature (Santoso & Bidayat, 2019) (Athapaththu & Kulathunga, 2018)
H6-There is a positive effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Perceived usefulness	0.470	0.000	Supported	Consistence with existing literature (Athapaththu & Kulathunga, 2018)

The results revealed that except for H4, all other five hypotheses were supported.

Conclusion

This research found that Perceived Ease of Use has a significant positive effect on Perceived usefulness. Further, it was found that Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness significantly and positively affect Attitude towards Internet use. The research also established that Attitude towards Internet use and Trust have significant positive effects on Online purchase intention among young adults.

Research Implications

This study has both theoretical and practical implications. The findings of this study help to fill the existing knowledge gap, especially in the local context, in relation to online purchase intention among young adults. The practitioners can focus on the significant findings of this study to enhance Attitude towards Internet use and Online purchase intention among young adults. Accordingly, online shoppers can take measures to increase the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of online shopping. This should increase attitude towards online shopping, which will lead to an increased intention towards online shopping, benefitting the online shoppers. Further, the online shoppers should focus on improving the trust aspect of online shopping as it is directly related to the online shopping intention of young adults

Research limitations and future research suggestions

The study has a couple of limitations. First, this study focused on undergraduates in Sri Lanka; hence, their opinion may not reflect those of the Sri Lankan people in general. Second, the study focused on a limited number of factors affecting online purchase intention. Hence, the future researcher may consider a larger sample representing a wider customer base and incorporate more constructs in their studies.

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